

GRAMMARING SKILLS OF GRADE 8 TEACHERS AND STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN CLUSTER 10 DIVISION OF SANTA ROSA CITY

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ABSTRACT

The main tenet of this research was to determine the level of Grade 8 teachers' grammaring skills and the level of students' communicative competence in Cluster 10 Division of Sta. Rosa City. The study employed a quantitative research approach with a descriptive correlational design, involving seven Grade 8 teachers and 150 students from Don Jose Integrated High School, Pulong Sta. Cruz National High School, and Santo Domingo Integrated High School, who were selected through stratified random sampling. The instruments used for data gathering were researcher-made survey questionnaires divided into sections assessing teachers' grammaring skills and students' communicative competence. The collected data were subjected to various statistical treatments, including sample size, mean, standard deviation, frequency, percentage, T-test, and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson's r). The results indicated that the teachers' grammaring skills in form (structure), meaning (semantics), and use (pragmatics) were rated as very good, while students' communicative competence, including grammatical, discourse, strategic, and sociocultural dimensions, was rated as good. Additionally, there was a significant relationship between the Grade 8 teachers' grammaring skills and the students' communicative competence, leading to a significant correlation for both respondents. However, no significant difference was found in the grammatical dimension. Overall, a significant difference was observed between the respondents' grammaring skills and communicative competence. In conclusion, based on the evaluation and analysis of the collected data, the proposed English Language Literacy (TELL) Enhancement Program may aid in transforming students into effective and knowledgeable language users.

Keywords: *Grammaring Skills, Communicative Competence*

INTRODUCTION

Language is a dynamic tool essential for human communication, encompassing linguistic structures, cultural nuances, educational contexts, and the impact of technology. In education, language significantly influences a learner's academic success and life outcomes, shaped by teacher expectations and the teaching-learning process.

Despite its importance, the teaching and learning process faces numerous challenges (Lumentut & Lengkoan, 2021), including diverse learning styles, behavior management, and English Language Proficiency (ELP). Traditionally, language learning focuses on listening, speaking, reading, and writing. However, "grammaring" as a fifth skill emphasizes teaching and practicing grammar in context, enhancing effective and meaningful language use.

In the Philippines, language education is challenged by multilingual environments, educational disparities, traditional teaching methods, teacher training, cultural attitudes, technology access, and assessment practices. Santos et al. (2022) noted that early language learning can improve competencies in Sta. Rosa City.

Today's students are self-directed, social media-dependent, and information-driven, but they often have short attention spans and lack interest. Emphasizing communicative competence within grammaring represents a pedagogical shift towards practical grammar use in real-life communication. TursoniBrosethca(2021) and Byram highlighted the importance of intercultural skills alongside linguistic proficiency, recognizing the interconnectedness of language, culture, and communication in a globalized world.

Further, Tursonovich (2022) stressed that consistent exposure to natural communication fosters communicative competence. Learners should express themselves freely in English and develop an English personality. The relationship between grammaring and communicative competence is vital for language proficiency, with grammaring providing a foundation for accurate and contextually appropriate language use.

This study investigated the grammaring skills of Grade 8 teachers and students' communicative competence to support The English Language Literacy (TELL) Enhancement Program. This intervention aims to improve English language instruction, enhancing students' confidence and proficiency in spoken and written English.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the relationship between the grammaring skills of Grade 8 teachers and their students' communicative competence of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City.

Specifically, the researcher sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of grammaring skills of Grade 8 English Teachers of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City in terms of:
 - 1.1 Form (Structure),
 - 1.2 Meaning (Semantics), and
 - 1.3 Use (Pragmatics)?
2. What is the student's level of communicative competence of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City as assessed by the Grade 8 Teachers and Students:
 - 2.1 Grammatical Competence,
 - 2.2 Discourse Competence,
 - 2.3 Strategic Competence; and
 - 2.4 Sociolinguistic Competence?
3. Is there a significant difference between the level of communicative competence as assessed by the Grade 8 teachers and students?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the English teachers' grammaring skills and their students' communicative competence?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what program can be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

The study used a descriptive-correlational research design to explore the relationship between Grade 8 teachers' grammaring skills and students' communicative competence in Cluster 10, Division of Santa Rosa City. The research was conducted in three public secondary schools, involving seven teachers and 150 students. Stratified random sampling was used to select participants. Data were collected using researcher-made survey questionnaires, which included a 21-item Likert scale for teachers' grammaring skills and a 22-item Likert scale for students' communicative competence. The instruments were validated through expert review and reliability testing (Cronbach's Alpha: .988 for grammaring skills and .707 for communicative competence). Data analysis involved statistical methods such as mean, standard deviation, t-test, and Pearson's r. Ethical considerations included obtaining consent and ensuring confidentiality.

RESULTS

1. **What is the Level of Grammaring Skills of Grade 8 English Teachers of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City in terms of:**
 - 1.1 **Form (Structure)**

Table 1.1

Level of Grammaticing Skills of Grade 8 English Teachers of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City in terms of Form (Structure)

<i>Asan English Teacher, I_</i>	X	VI
1. usually start teaching simple verbal concepts and relate them to sentence structure.	3.57	VG
2. scaffold the learning of grammar through practice and application	3.43	VG
3. usually emphasize the key points in sentence combining	3.43	VG
4. allow learners to create context in role playing in learning the form and structure.	3.29	VG
5. usually take time to talk with my students and ask them questions that require answers with particular structure.	3.00	G
6. integrate ICT or online games during the discussions of the form and structure.	3.14	G
7. utilize localized and contextualized texts in teaching form and structure among the students.	3.43	VG
General Assessment	3.33	VG

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG) 2.50 – 3.24 Agree – Good (G) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree – Poor (P)

1.2 Meaning (Semantics)

Table 1.2

Level of Grammaticing Skills of Grade 8 English Teachers of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City in terms of Meaning (Semantics)

<i>As English Teacher, I_</i>	X	VI
1. point out and discuss new words as we read together.	3.71	VG
2. emphasize the importance of context clues in learning synonyms and antonyms.	3.71	VG
3. let learners express their difficulties in learning new words and address their needs.	3.57	VG
4. let them classify the words and make sure to make connections among the words.	3.14	G
5. teach the students to recognize words from their definition.	3.43	VG
6. give students one new word in a day, discuss its meaning and how to use it.	3.14	G
7. teach the students varied strategies in learning the meaning of the word.	3.29	VG
General Assessment	3.43	VG

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG) 2.50 – 3.24 Agree – Good (G) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree – Poor (P)

1.3 Use (Pragmatics)

Table 1.3

Level of Grammaticing Skills of Grade 8 English Teachers of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City in terms of Use (Pragmatics)

<i>As English Teacher, I_</i>	X	VI
1. impart the learners the use and understanding of the non-verbal cues.	3.57	VG
2. model in terms of good listening for the students to realize when to speak and when to listen.	3.71	VG
3. always use appropriate volume and tone.	3.71	VG
4. teach learners the proper ways of delivering a speech.	3.29	VG
5. let learners collaborate with other learners.	3.14	G
6. usually encourage positive peer interactions where empathy, respect, and kindness will be integrated as well	3.86	VG
7. incorporate social skills into the students' daily routines and activities.	3.71	VG
General Assessment	3.57	VG

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG) 2.50 – 3.24 Agree – Good (G) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree – Poor (P)

2. What is the student's level of communicative competence of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City as assessed by the Grade 8 Teachers and Students:

2.1 Grammatical Competence

Table 2.1

Students Level of Communicative Competence as assessed by the Grade 8 English Teachers and Students of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City in terms of Grammatical Competence

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
<i>As English Teacher and Student, I_</i>						
1. can speak English like native speakers do.	3.00	G	2.75	G	2.88	G
2. can easily identify grammatical errors in sentences.	2.57	G	2.63	G	2.60	G
3. can logically arrange my ideas in delivering an effective speech.	3.14	G	2.77	G	2.96	G
4. am familiar with grammar rules particularly subject-verb agreement.	3.00	G	2.75	G	2.88	G
5. know well how to construct different sentence structures.	2.43	F	2.73	G	2.58	G
6. can accurately quote what I have read in English.	3.14	G	3.01	G	3.08	G

General Assessment	2.82	G	2.77	G	2.80	G
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Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG) 2.50 – 3.24 Agree – Good (G)
1.75 – 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree – Poor (P)

2.2. Discourse Competence

Table 2.2

Students Level of Communicative Competence as assessed by the Grade 8 English Teachers and Students of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City in terms of Discourse Competence

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Composite	
<i>As English Teacher and Student, I_</i>	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI
1. can logically arrange sentences to form an effective essay.	3.29	VG	2.79	G	3.04	G
2. know when and how to use cohesive devices.	3.29	VG	2.65	G	2.97	G
3. can paraphrase and modify a text or paragraph.	3.43	VG	2.72	G	3.08	G
4. can easily identify the theme of a certain text.	3.71	VG	2.66	G	3.19	G
5. am skillful in terms of text construction and interpretation.	2.86	G	2.78	G	2.82	G
6. can deliver a speech with cohesion and meaning.	3.00	G	2.74	G	2.87	G
General Assessment	3.29	VG	2.72	G	3.01	G

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG) 2.50 – 3.24 Agree – Good (G)
1.75 – 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree – Poor (P)

2.3. Strategic Competence

Table 2.3

Students' Level of Communicative Competence as assessed by the Grade 8 English Teachers and Students of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City in terms of Strategic Competence

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Composite	
<i>As English Teacher and Student, I_</i>	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI
1. can paraphrase what the speaker has said.	3.71	VG	2.86	G	3.29	VG

2. can ask related questions during our class discussions.	3.29	VG	2.92	G	3.11	G
3. can retell the information have received in detail.	3.57	VG	2.91	G	3.24	G
4. can easily share my thoughts and insights during group collaborations.	3.43	VG	2.92	G	3.18	G
5. can speak in English spontaneously with confidence.	2.29	G	2.77	G	2.53	G
General Assessment	3.26	VG	2.88	G	3.07	G

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG) 2.50 – 3.24 Agree – Good (G) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree – Poor (P)

2.4. Sociolinguistic

Table 2.4

Students' Level of Communicative Competence as assessed by the Grade 8 English Teachers and Students of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City in terms of Sociolinguistic Competence

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Composite	
<i>As English Teacher and Student, I...</i>	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. can express positive feelings and emotions.	3.71	VG	3.19	G	3.45	VG
2. answer questions in discussions with respect.	4.00	VG	3.23	G	3.62	VG
3. use friendly facial expressions in communication.	3.71	VG	3.13	G	3.42	VG
4. welcome healthy arguments.	3.57	VG	3.13	G	3.35	VG
5. can listen to others and experience empathy.	3.86	VG	3.06	G	3.46	VG
General Assessment	3.77	VG	3.15	G	3.46	VG

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG) 2.50 – 3.24 Agree – Good (G) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree – Poor (P)

3. Is there a significant difference between the Level of Communicative Competence as assessed by the Grade 8 Teachers and Students?

Table 3

Test of Significant Difference Between the Level of Communicative Competence as assessed by the Grade 8 Teachers and Students

Variables	t test	p value	Remarks	Decision
Grammatical Competence	.419	.686	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Discourse Competence	7.882	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Strategic Competence	2.016	.014	Significant	Reject Ho
Sociolinguistic Competence	9.397	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

4. Is there a significant relationship between the Teachers' Grammaring Skills and the Students' Communicative Competence?

Table 4

Test of Significant Relationship between the Grade 8 Teachers' Grammaring Skills and the Students' Communicative Competence

Grammaring Skills	Students' Communicative Competence	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Form (Structure)	Grammatical	.845*	.017	Significant	Reject ho
	Discourse	.173	.710	Not Significant	Accept ho
	Strategic	-.115	.807	Not Significant	Accept ho
	Sociolinguistic	.124	.791	Not Significant	Accept ho
Meaning (Semantics)	Grammatical	.444	.319	Not Significant	Accept ho
	Discourse	-.109	.816	Not Significant	Accept ho
	Strategic	-.547	.203	Not Significant	Accept ho
Use (Pragmatics)	Sociolinguistic	.091	.846	Not Significant	Accept ho
	Grammatical	.795*	.033	Significant	Reject ho
	Discourse	.561	.190	Not Significant	Accept ho
	Strategic	.197	.672	Not Significant	Accept ho
	Sociolinguistic	.427	.339	Not Significant	Accept ho

5. Based on the findings of the study, what program may be proposed?

The English Language Literacy (TELL) Enhancement Program

Key Result Areas	Objectives	Strategies / Activities	Persons Involved	Time Frame	Funds	Success Indicator
1. Grammatical Competence	Familiarize with the rules of subject – verb agreement and use correct form of the verb	The teacher will provide exercises on identifying subject of the sentence, subjects as singular or plural and the correct subject-verb agreement rule.	English Coordinator English Teachers	August 2023	Human Resource	95% of the objective have been attained
2. Discourse Competence	Use appropriate cohesive devices and compose informative speech.	The teacher will provide exercises on using cohesive devices appropriately and will ask students to compose an informative speech.	Grade 8 Students		Financial Resource	
3. Discourse competence	Can Paraphrase what the		English Coordinator	September 2023		95% of the objective have been attained

4.Sociolinguistic competence

speaker has said.

The students will be given several sets of listening activities and will paraphrase what the speaker has said.

Express positive feelings and emotions

The teacher has an oral or writing activity: getting students to discuss personal experiences, reading, and discussing the messages in dialogues, analyzing idiomatic expressions.

English Teachers

Grade 8 Students

November 2023

December 2023

Human Resource

Financial Resource

95% of the objective have been attained .

95% of the objective have been attained .

DISCUSSION

1. What is the Level of Gramming Skills of Grade 8 English Teachers of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City in terms of:

Form (Structure)

Table 1.1 Level of Gramming Skills of Grade 8 English Teachers of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City in terms of Form (Structure)

The English teacher's grammaring skills level in terms of form(structure) was Very Good (3.33). The indicator "As English Teacher, I usually start teaching simple verbal concepts and relate them to sentence structure" had the highest mean of 3.57 and was verbally interpreted as Very Good, while the indicator "As English Teacher, I usually take time to talk with my students and ask them questions that require answers with particular structure" had the lowest computed mean of 3.00 which was verbally interpreted as Good.

The findings imply that the level of teachers' grammaring skills in terms of form (structure) assists students in recognizing grammatical forms, using grammar creatively, and participating more actively in class. To put it simply, if they are aware of grammatical form, they ought to comprehend its structure, rules, and applications in communication.

Schurz et.al (2023) pointed out that grammar in the context of form focused instruction encouraged the systematic teaching of grammatical characteristics, such that both students and the teacher perceived the activities' objective as being the advancement of form-based knowledge. Further, form-focused instruction was a strategy for helping students focus on the structure required for language formation and emphasized comprehension.

Zarinfard et al. (2021) suggested that using a flipped classroom on learning outcomes in a general English course focusing on grammar and vocabulary facilitated teachers' capacity to extend and provide the learning process beyond the classroom, freeing up time for other important topics to be discussed in class. Additionally, the value of blended learning, especially utilizing technology to target students' learning issues while improving learning competencies and student motivation was essential.

1.2 Meaning (Semantics)

Level of Gramming Skills of Grade 8 English Teachers of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City in terms of Meaning (Semantics)

The English teachers' grammaring skills level in terms of meaning (semantics) was Very Good (3.43). The indicators "As English Teacher, I point out and discuss new words as we read together," and "As English teacher, I emphasize the importance of context clues in learning synonyms and antonyms." got the highest computed mean of 3.71 and were

verbally interpreted as Very Good, while the indicators “As English Teacher, I let them classify the words and make sure to make connections among the words.” and “As English teacher, I give students one new word in a day, discuss its meaning and how to use it.” got the lowest computed mean of 3.14 which was verbally interpreted as Good.

The findings indicate that the teachers’ grammaring skills in terms of meaning (semantics) occur during communication and, more crucially, through mutual understanding. This is a harmonious mixture of broad information, comprehending words and phrases, and applying practical experience so as the capacity to realize and internalize ideas and intentions in context the way humans do.

Kaljanov (2023) clarified that grammatical meaning was the value generated by the relationship of a word with other words in the sentence. Thus, the grammatical form of a word and its grammatical meaning were closely related. On the other hand, Broseth and Nygard (2023) determined that grammatical understanding was very limited to word classes, verbs, noun, adjectives, and pronouns, as well as the sentence's constituent subject. Their insight was based on semantics. Moreover, Tilavova (2023) underscored that semantics played an important role in education because it aided teachers and learners to learn and be aware of word meanings, sentence connections, discourse, and context. Putting importance to semantic fields paved the way in grasping how words and their connections related to one another, since this greatly influenced reading comprehension, how they perceived others, and even the decisions they made because of their interpretation.

1.3 Use (Pragmatics)

Table 1.3

Level of Grammaring Skills of Grade 8 English Teachers of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City in terms of Use (Pragmatics)

The English teachers’ grammaring skills level in terms of Use (Pragmatics) was Very Good (3.57). The indicators “As English Teacher, I model in terms of good listening for the students to realize when to speak and when to listen,” “As English teacher, I always use appropriate volume and tone.” and “As English teacher, I incorporate social skills into the students’ daily routines and activities.” got the same highest mean of 3.71 verbally interpreted as Very Good, while the indicator “As English Teacher, I let learners collaborate with other learners.” had the lowest computed mean of 3.14 which was verbally interpreted as Good.

The findings imply that the teachers’ grammaring skills in terms of use (pragmatics) enable them to teach and learn English using conversational and practical activities. It also advances communicative linguistic instruction using targeted usage of language, especially in social functions.

Ishihara and Porcellato (2021) stated that most teachers considered their pragmatic ability to deal successfully across cultures, think, and behave appropriately, and interact

with learners from other cultural backgrounds. Farinde and Oyedokun-Alli (2020) highlighted the cooperative principle—a concept introduced by philosopher H. Paul Grice, pointing out that engaging in a meaningful conversation with quantity, quality, manner, and relevance attempted an informative, truthful, relevant, and clear discussion.

2. What is the student’s level of communicative competence of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City as assessed by the Grade 8 Teachers and Students:

Students Level of Communicative Competence as assessed by the Grade 8 English Teachers and Students of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City in terms of Grammatical Competence

The students’ level of communicative competence as assessed by teachers and students in terms of Grammatical Competence was Good (2.80). The indicator “As English Teacher and Student, I can accurately quote what I have read in English” had the highest composite mean of 3.08 and was verbally interpreted as Good, while the indicator “As English Teacher and Student, I know well how to construct different sentence structures” had the lowest composite mean of 2.58 which was verbally interpreted as Good.

This suggests that while students generally perform well in quoting what they have read, there might be some room for improvement in their ability to construct diverse sentence structures.

Qobilovna (2023) stated that the integrativeness of a teacher’s communicative competence, which was “consistency (co-level) between his/her value orientations, knowledge, practical skills and real behavior manifested in the process of pedagogical communication”, presupposes several substantive components, such as personal dispositions, knowledge, and communication skills.

It is important to note that when solving the problem of improving and developing a teacher’s communicative competence, it is difficult to be guided by a limited understanding of the term “communicative competence,” reducing its content to a set of communicative skills and abilities, although it is the latter that should be considered as the core, or nuclear, formation of the entire system of communicative competence teacher. In fact, communicative competence is, firstly, a personal quality of a teacher, formed in the process of development and self-development of the individual; secondly, an indicator of the teacher’s awareness of the goals, essence, structure, means, and features of pedagogical communication; level of proficiency in the relevant technology; individual psychological qualities of a specialist; desire for continuous improvement of communication activities; orientation towards a person’s personality as the main value,

as well as the ability to non-standard, creative solutions to problems arising in the process of pedagogical communication. source Turko et al. (2021).

2.2. Discourse Competence

Students Level of Communicative Competence as assessed by the Grade 8 English Teachers and Students of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City in terms of Discourse Competence

The students' level of communicative competence as assessed by teachers and students in terms of discourse competence was Good (3.01). The indicator "As English Teacher and Student, I can easily identify the theme of a certain text." had the highest composite mean of 3.19 and was verbally interpreted as Good while the indicator "As English Teacher and Student, I am skillful in terms of text construction and interpretation." had the lowest composite mean of 2.82 which was verbally interpreted as Good.

The results indicate that although students typically perform well in identifying themes within texts, there is potential for enhancement in their proficiency when it comes to constructing and interpreting texts.

Gray and Rangelova (2023) cited that Dell Hymes initially coined the term in 1966 when reacting against the perceived deficiency of Noam Chomsky's contrast between performance and competence consequently dived into the ethnographic exploration of communicative competence to address the abstract notion of competence. He discovered that people speak differently in unique situations, which is a fact that most should accept as positive. Hymes' use of the term has evolved into what it is today. When both sides were balanced, language fluency came into play. To put it simply, communicative competence referred to how effectively one can communicate with someone else.

2.3. Strategic Competence

Students' Level of Communicative Competence as assessed by the Grade 8 English Teachers and Students of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City in terms of Strategic Competence

The students' level of communicative competence as assessed by teachers and students in terms of strategic competence was Good (3.07). The indicator "As English Teacher and Student, I can paraphrase what the speaker has said." had the highest composite mean of 3.29 and was verbally interpreted as Very Good while the indicator "As English Teacher and Student, I can speak in English spontaneously with confidence." had the lowest composite mean of 2.53 which was verbally interpreted as Good.

The findings imply that although students demonstrate proficiency in rephrasing spoken material, there's a need for enhancement in their confidence and ability to speak English spontaneously.

Alem (2020) cited that strategic competence was one type of communicative competence among others which had been postulated by Canale and Swain in 1980. Strategic

competence defined by Canale and Swain (1980, as cited in Thurrell, 1991), and was affirmed by Alem (2020) as 'verbal and non-verbal communication strategies that may be called into action to compensate for breakdowns in communication due to performance variables or to insufficient competence. Further, Alem (2020) also shown that communicative competence incorporates at least three: grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, and strategic competence. Strategic competence refers to the ability to get one's meaning across successfully to communicative partners, especially when problems arise in the communication process. Strategic competence is relevant since communication breakdowns occur and must be overcome not only in a foreign language but in one's mother tongue as well.

Bachman (1990, as cited in Alem, 2020) said that strategic competence embraced all aspects of the assessment, planning, and execution of communicative tasks. He saw strategic competence not only as a component of communicative competence but also as a more general cognitive capacity. These components together comprise "a set of meta-cognitive processes, or strategies," which can be thought of as higher-order executive processes that provide a cognitive management function in language use, as well as in other cognitive activities". Those other cognitive activities included language learning and all its ramifications.

2.4. Sociolinguistic

Students' Level of Communicative Competence as assessed by the Grade 8 English Teachers and Students of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City in terms of Sociolinguistic Competence

The students' level of communicative competence as assessed by teachers and students in terms of sociolinguistic competence was Good (3.46). The indicator "As English Teacher and Student, I answer questions in discussions with respect." had the highest composite mean of 3.62 and was verbally interpreted as Very Good, while the indicator "As English Teacher and Student, I welcome healthy arguments." had the lowest composite mean of 3.35 which was verbally interpreted as Very Good.

The results indicate that students typically exhibit respectful behavior during discussions. However, there is an opportunity for them to enhance their ability to actively participate in constructive arguments within the classroom. This improvement could significantly enhance their proficiency in the English language. According to Nordquist (2019), sociolinguistic competence included knowledge of sociocultural rules of use. It was concerned with the learners' ability to handle for example settings, topics, and communicative functions in different sociolinguistic contexts. In addition, it dealt with the use of appropriate grammatical forms for different communicative functions in different sociolinguistic contexts.

Moreover, Garcia-Martinez, et al. (2022) stated that sociolinguistic competence also addressed adequate application of the sociocultural rules of language, with this being of great significance in the work of the teacher, both for the development of their professional teaching identity and for the establishment of interactive processes with members of the

educational community. A high level of sociolinguistic competence, as much in the normative as the communicative field, was an essential quality for future teachers to carry out teaching-learning processes. These included promoting cooperative working and developing the teacher's relationship with families, institutions, and other teachers. These were becoming increasingly essential processes.

2. Is there a significant difference between the Level of Communicative Competence as assessed by the Grade 8 Teachers and Students?

Test of Significant Difference Between the Level of Communicative Competence as assessed by the Grade 8 Teachers and Students

The generated computed inferential statistics values for the Discourse, Strategic, and Sociolinguistic were .000, .014, and .000 respectively, which were less than the level of significance at .05, thus the null hypothesis was rejected. Meanwhile, for the Grammatical Competence, it has a generated computed inferential statistic value of .686 which is greater than the level of significance at .05, thus the null hypothesis was accepted.

Therefore, there is no significant difference between the Grade 8 Teachers' and Students' Communicative Competence in terms of grammatical competence. But overall, there is a major significant difference between the Grade 8 Teachers' and Students' Communicative Competence.

As shown in Table 4, the t test of all the variables were interpreted with negligible positive correlation to correlate Gramming skills and Students' Communicative Competence, and the computed probability values were lesser than the level of significance ($P < 0.05$); thus, the null hypothesis is majorly rejected or statistically significant. The result shows that there is major significance in the relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

Most correlations suggest a significant relationship between the independent and dependent variables. However, concerning grammatical competence, the table indicates no significant association between these variables. This observation concerns the relationship between variables rather than differences.

It can be concluded that the Gramming skills have significant relationship with Grade 8 teachers and their students' communicative competence of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City. These results suggest a discrepancy in the significance attributed to these factors by teachers and students. While students prioritize the capacity to express opinions and participate in communicative tasks for enhancing their communicative competence, teachers focus more on cultivating general educational skills and fostering motivation. This variance underscores the necessity for a nuanced approach to language education, where a balance between student-centered communicative activities and

teacher-directed educational methods is crucial for fostering effective language development.

According to Kakhramonovich (2021), what people should be looking for now was a consensus in the field on the types of communicative competence that existed and appropriate terminology to describe them so that they can move forward in their understanding of how the various components interacted with each other and their relative importance in language learning. He also cited that grammatical and pragmatic competencies were closely associated with each other while sociolinguistic competence was distinct. Communicative competence, as it had been outlined so far, had recently been criticized by several writers because it modeled itself on educated native speakers and took their communicative competence as the goal of foreign language learning.

4. Is there a significant relationship between the Teachers' Gramming Skills and the Students' Communicative Competence?

Test of Significant Relationship between the Grade 8 Teachers' Gramming Skills and the Students' Communicative Competence

The generated computed probability values were .710, .807, .791, .319, .816, .203, .846, .190, .672, and .339 which were greater than the level of significance at .05, thus the null hypothesis was majorly accepted. However, in the Form (Structure) and Use (Pragmatics) in terms of both grammatical competence, which were .017 and .033 respectively, which were lower than the level of significance, the null hypothesis in the competencies is rejected. Therefore, there is significant relationship between the Grade 8 Teachers' Gramming Skills and the Students' Communicative Competence.

These findings emphasize the need to understand the intricate interplay between teachers' proficiency in grammar instruction and students' ability to effectively communicate. They suggest that the effectiveness of language learning experiences depends not only on students' communicative competence but also on teachers' grammatical skills. Therefore, it is essential to implement focused interventions that address both aspects.

By targeting both teacher and student competencies, these interventions can contribute to more robust language learning outcomes. Students can develop a deeper understanding of language structures and functions, while teachers can refine their instructional practices to better support student learning. Ultimately, this holistic approach can lead to more effective language learning experiences and improved proficiency for all stakeholders involved.

While most of the correlation resulted to not having significance in the relationship between the independent and dependent variable, the table shows that in grammaring skills, specifically in Form (Structure) and Use (Pragmatics), both in terms of grammatical competence, the results states that there is a significant relationship between the independent and dependent variable. It can be concluded that the Gramming skills

have no significant relationship with Grade 8 teachers and their students' communicative competence of Cluster 10 in the Division of Santa Rosa City.

Both variables do not greatly affect and impact one another due to difference in outcomes and perspectives. The role of communicative competence for students is primarily having the ability to express their opinions and development of communicative phenomena while for teachers is having the prerequisite of building motivation and development of general educational skills, the insignificance is notably evident.

According to Choi (2022) communicative competence is dynamic rather than a static concept that depends on the negotiation of meaning between two or more persons who share some knowledge of the language. Further, the dynamic and context-specific nature of communicative competence, enrich our understanding of its complexities in contemporary language education and intercultural communication research.

5. Based on the findings of the study, what program may be proposed?

As an output, in consideration of the results of the survey conducted among the teachers and students, there will be a professional development plan to be conducted to give teacher an avenue for professional growth and enhancement focusing on the strategies in teaching English in terms of form, meaning, and use. Likewise, as part of the program, learners will be given an enhancement plan in grammar.

The English Language Literacy Enhancement Program, also known as TELL Program, aims to develop and improve literacy among students in terms of grammaring skills and communicative competence. The given strategies and time frame of the program are sufficient to transform learners into communicative competent language users. It is important to not just teach and fixate on what language is all about, but there should also be the essence of empowerment and transforming learners into responsible and effective language users.

Conclusions

1. The findings suggest that teachers' skills in grammaring significantly enhance students' grammatical understanding and active participation in class. Specifically, teachers' proficiency in grammatical form (structure) helps students recognize and use grammatical forms creatively, and understand grammar's rules and applications in communication. Teachers' grammaring skills in meaning (semantics) are vital during communication, fostering mutual understanding through a blend of extensive knowledge, comprehension of words and phrases, and practical experience. This enables students to grasp and internalize ideas and intentions in context. Additionally, teachers' skills in the use (pragmatics) of grammar promote effective English teaching and learning through conversational and practical activities, advancing

communicative linguistic instruction by focusing on language use in social functions.

2. The findings suggest that while students excel in quoting texts and identifying themes, they could improve their ability to construct diverse sentence structures and interpret texts more effectively. Additionally, although they are proficient in rephrasing spoken material, students need to build confidence and spontaneity in speaking English. Furthermore, while students generally show respectful behavior during discussions, there is room for them to enhance their active participation in constructive arguments, which would significantly boost their overall English proficiency.
3. The results reveal a discrepancy in priorities between teachers and students regarding language education. Students emphasize the importance of expressing opinions and participating in communicative tasks to improve their communicative competence, whereas teachers prioritize developing general educational skills and motivation. This difference highlights the need for a balanced approach that integrates student-centered communicative activities with teacher-directed educational methods to foster effective language development.
4. These findings highlight the importance of understanding the interplay between teachers' grammar instruction proficiency and students' communication skills. Effective language learning relies on both students' communicative competence and teachers' grammatical expertise. Thus, targeted interventions that enhance both areas are essential. By improving both teacher and student competencies, these interventions can lead to a deeper understanding of language structures for students and more refined instructional practices for teachers. This holistic approach aims to create more effective language learning experiences and improve proficiency for everyone involved.
5. That the proposed action plan, The English Language Literacy (TELL) Enhancement Program, will be a great contribution and significance for modern-day learners to be transformed into effective, responsible, and knowledgeable language users

Recommendations

From the inquiry conducted, certain recommendations were posited.

1. High school students may develop their skills in other competencies that may help them to cultivate a good foundation in learning not only language but all other disciplines which may help them to be globally ready and competitive.
2. Teachers may continue to engage them in professional development for their own growth and career advancement which may help them to be more competent in

their chosen craft. Likewise, they may provide appropriate intervention programs intended for the learners' academic improvement.

3. The school administrators and City Schools Division of Sta. Rosa may use the result of the study as reference points to further facilitate and implement efficacious, beneficial, and reliable action and enhancement programs that could empower students' grammaring skills and communicative competence.
 4. Grammar teaching and learning skills and competence serve their purpose and validate a significant impact on the learning of the students and teaching strategies of the teachers. Teachers may continuously improve their skills for the betterment of the teaching and learning process specifically in English. Moreover, other applicable strategies may be utilized for the benefit of teachers and students.
 5. Let TELL (The English Language Literacy) Enhancement Program be implemented and supported by the school's top officials for its success outcomes and mechanisms.
 6. Future researchers may utilize the results and findings of this study in conducting similar research endeavors. Likewise, they may also develop an applicable teaching and learning resources or plans that can be used for teaching and learning processes.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting the study, the author ensured strict adherence to ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were fully informed about the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights. Participants were assured of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any repercussions. The anonymity of all respondents was maintained by assigning codes and ensuring that no identifying information was included in the published results. The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded throughout the research process, ensuring that no harm, psychological or otherwise, came to them.

Furthermore, there were no conflicts of interest that influenced the conduct of this study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, with proper citations and acknowledgments given for all sources used. The interpretation of findings was conducted without any bias, ensuring an objective analysis of the data. Finally, the results of the study were used solely for research purposes, contributing to the academic and practical understanding of the grammaring skills of Grade 8 teachers and students' communicative competence.

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